

METAGENOME STUDIES ON THE MICROBIOME OF XYLELLA FASTIDIOSA-INFECTED OLIVES

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The CoDiRO strain of *Xylella fastidiosa* (*Xf*), which is devastating olive trees in the Apulia Region (southern Italy), represents the first documented establishment of this plant pathogenic bacterium in Europe. Diseases induced by *Xf* have no chemical cure and its pathogenic mechanism(s) are not completely understood. Nevertheless, profiles and relationships of microbial communities and their effects on the expression of symptoms of *Xf*-infected plants are poorly studied. The microbiome of *Xf*-infected olives was investigated by a shotgun metagenomic DNA sequencing approach that avoids the limitations of amplicon sequencing. 28,333,924 and 29,096,610 reads from *Xf*-infected and healthy plants were analyzed by MetaPhlAn, a metagenomic abundance estimation tool which maps reads to a set of selected marker sequences. A complex community of small symbiotic bacteria of insects, i.e. *Candidatus* Zinderia insecticola and *Candidatus* Carsonella ruddii represented the 31% and 22% of the total population was found in libraries from xylem tissues. In infected plants *Xf* reaches the 12% of the total microbial community. Studies are ongoing to characterize the microbial communities in the xylem sap of tolerant and susceptible olive cultivars, to develop a control strategy based on the manipulation of these resident communities and to identify endosymbiont(s) which may be used to reduce the severity of symptoms. Moreover, the evaluation of an endosymbiont bacterium for its potential to colonize *Xf*-infected olive tissues is underway.